

Intangible Assets at a Global Level

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The "Global Innovation Index" (GII) is an index that measures the innovation capacity of a country or region by evaluating various key indicators that influence the creation and development of innovation. Among these indicators, one fundamental aspect is that of "intangible assets", which refer to immaterial goods. These assets include elements such as intellectual property, trademarks, patents, industrial design, copyrights, and even technical and organizational skills. In an economy increasingly based on knowledge, intangible assets represent a highly valuable resource for companies and national economies, contributing significantly to technological progress and international competitiveness. In the context of the GII, intangible assets are analyzed to understand how effectively a country can transform intellectual and creative capital into concrete, marketable innovations. A high capacity for managing and protecting intangible assets can lead to the development of new ideas, products, and services that stimulate economic growth and productivity. For example, a legal system that adequately protects intellectual property rights incentivizes the creation of new patents, enhances investor confidence, and encourages research and development (R&D) activities. Additionally, intangible assets also encompass human capital, referring to the skills, training, and education of the workforce, which are crucial for sustaining an innovative ecosystem. A country's ability to attract and retain qualified talent also helps improve its position in the Global Innovation Index. In summary, within the framework of the GII, intangible assets are essential for evaluating a nation's innovation capacity, as they indicate the quality and efficiency with which intellectual and creative resources are managed and transformed into economic value. The data is available for the period from 2013 to 2022.

Global Intangible Assets in 2022. The 2022 data on intangible assets, provided by the Global Innovation Index (GII), reveals a significant disparity in the ability of various countries to leverage and manage these immaterial goods. These assets include intellectual property such as patents and copyrights, human capital, brands, and design. These elements are crucial for stimulating economic growth, enhancing competitiveness, and fostering innovation. Analyzing the data, significant trends emerge that reflect the state of the knowledge economy on a global scale. At the top of the rankings, we find South Korea with a score of 85.7, followed by China with 82.9 and France with 76.9. South Korea, which has built a solid reputation as a technological and industrial hub, leads the group thanks to its strong commitment to research and development (R&D), intellectual property protection, and the training of a highly skilled workforce. Its large companies, such as Samsung and LG, have fueled a culture of innovation supported by government policies aimed at strengthening intangible assets. China has also emerged as a rising power, driven by massive investments in R&D, a dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem, and aggressive policies for intellectual property protection. The result is a massive growth in the number of registered patents and trademarks. France, ranked third, represents Europe with a strong ability to transform human capital into intangible assets through innovation in sectors such as aerospace, automotive, and luxury goods, where design and brand are determining

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factors. Continuing with the analysis, it is noticeable that countries like Germany, the United Kingdom, and Switzerland, traditionally known for their innovative capacities, are positioned at a relatively lower level than expected. For example, Germany scores 67.8, the United Kingdom 68.3, and Switzerland 63.5. This may reflect a slower transition toward greater emphasis on intangible assets compared to Asian countries such as South Korea and China. While these countries remain leaders in technological and scientific innovation, their performance in terms of managing and exploiting intangible assets might not be keeping pace with the dynamism of other emerging nations. Switzerland, known for its financial sector, could be disadvantaged by the fact that intangible assets increasingly require technological and digital innovations, which are growing more rapidly in other parts of the world. Surprisingly, countries like Malta (69.6) and Turkey (72.2) are ranked higher than the United States (52.8) and Japan (53.8). Turkey has significantly invested in its technological infrastructure and human capital, encouraging the development of tech startups and increasing the production of patents and trademarks. Malta, a small island state, has capitalized on its strategic position within the European Union to attract investment in knowledge-intensive sectors such as fintech and iGaming. The United States, historically a global leader in innovation, may be penalized in this index by growing international competition and a relative slowdown in protecting its intangible assets compared to other nations. In the middle of the ranking, we find countries like Italy (62.2) and Iran (60.2), positioned similarly. Italy, although internationally recognized for its design, branding, and innovation in sectors such as fashion and automotive, might be hindered by bureaucratic inefficiencies and a lower capacity for intellectual property protection. Iran, despite economic and political challenges, managed to achieve a competitive score thanks to its strong human capital base, with a growing number of scientific and technological patents. In the second half of the ranking, countries such as Brazil (41.8), Russia (40), and India (38) stand out, all of which are large emerging economies with vast populations and rapidly growing domestic markets. However, their performance in intangible assets remains below expectations. These countries, despite having significant innovation potential, face challenges related to intellectual property rights protection, the quality of human capital, and the ability to transform knowledge into tangible economic goods. For example, India has a vibrant tech startup ecosystem, but its relatively low position in the GII reflects difficulties in scaling and protecting intangible assets on a larger scale. At the bottom of the ranking, we find countries such as Niger (0.1), Mali (0.9), and Iraq (0.7), highlighting the deep disparity in innovation capacity worldwide. These countries, often affected by political instability, conflicts, and inadequate infrastructure, struggle to develop economic systems based on intangible assets. The poor quality of human capital, combined with an underdeveloped entrepreneurial environment and an almost total lack of intellectual property protection, contributes to keeping these countries at the lowest positions in the index. Lastly, examining the position of some European countries such as Spain (50.6), Finland (46), and Norway (32.9), it becomes apparent that, despite advanced technological environments and high quality of life, these countries may not prioritize intangible asset development to the same extent as other emerging or developing economies. This could be due to a difference in innovation approaches, where emerging countries use intangible assets as leverage to accelerate economic growth, while more developed countries continue to focus on traditional sectors. In conclusion, the data on "intangible assets" from the Global Innovation Index 2022 show a highly diversified global landscape, where countries like South Korea and China are fully exploiting the potential of their intangible assets to foster innovation and economic growth. Other developed countries, such as the United States and Germany, face growing international competition, while many emerging economies are making significant strides in the valuation of intangible assets. However, a significant part of the world remains behind in terms of innovation capacity, with severe inequalities reflecting the need for targeted policies to promote education, intellectual property protection, and human capital development.

Global Intangible Assets Between 2013 and 2022. The data on intangible assets between 2013 and 2022 reveal an extremely diversified dynamic among countries, with significant changes both positive and negative. These assets, which include intellectual property, trademarks, patents, and human capital, play a key role in economic development, technological progress, and global competitiveness. Starting with the countries with the most significant increase, Iran experienced the greatest improvement in absolute terms, with an increase of 35.6 points, corresponding to a percentage growth of 144.7%. This increase can be attributed to greater attention to intellectual property protection, despite economic challenges and international sanctions. Iran has significantly invested in human capital development, particularly in scientific and technological sectors, leading to an increase in its capacity for innovation and exploitation of intangible assets. Countries like South Korea and China, with respective increases of 42.1 and 40.1 points, also recorded impressive progress, although their percentage growth was lower than Iran's. However, both South Korea and China exemplify how massive investments in research and development, human capital, and intellectual property protection can accelerate economic growth and foster international competitiveness. South Korea, with its large technology companies like Samsung and LG, has made valuing intangible assets a strategic priority, while China, on a rapid ascent, has seen an explosion in patent and trademark creation. Among European countries, France registered an increase of 32.9 points, a growth of 74.8%, demonstrating a high capacity for innovation in sectors such as aerospace, luxury goods, and automotive, where design and intellectual property are fundamental. However, other European countries, such as Germany and the United Kingdom, while recording increases (15.2 and 20.2 points, respectively), saw lower percentage growth compared to other emerging countries. This may indicate greater stability in their already advanced innovation systems, but also growing competition from emerging economies. Another country that registered notable growth was Uzbekistan, with an increase of 72.2%, although the absolute increase was only 5.2 points. This is a positive sign for an economy that is increasingly opening up to foreign investment and economic reforms. In Asia, Japan also improved its position, with an increase of 20.5 points and growth of 61.6%, continuing to represent a global technological powerhouse, although it has been surpassed by countries like South Korea and China in the past decade. However, while many countries recorded improvements, a significant part of the world saw a sharp decline in performance concerning intangible assets. For example, countries such as Saudi Arabia, which lost 36.3 points, and Qatar, which registered a decrease of 40.2 points, experienced significant downturns, with percentage drops of 53% and 53.6%, respectively. This decline may reflect difficulties in diversifying their economies beyond the oil and gas sector, especially in the context of growing global demand for technological and digital innovation. Similarly, countries like the United Arab Emirates, traditionally considered regional economic hubs, saw a decline of 54.1%, possibly due to a reduced emphasis on protecting and developing intangible assets in their economic diversification process. Another noteworthy case is the decline in Switzerland, which lost 8.7 points, corresponding to a 12% drop. Considered one of the most advanced economies in terms of innovation, this decline could signal a slight slowdown in its ability to maintain its leadership in the knowledge economy, although it remains one of the leading countries in the sector. Similarly, countries such as Canada (-11.7 points, -22.7%) and Finland (-9 points, -16.4%) saw moderate declines, perhaps due to growing international competition and saturation in their domestic innovation markets. The most drastic decline is observed in Sub-Saharan African and Southeast Asian countries, with nations such as Mali (-98.4%), Benin (-99.2%), and Niger (-99.1%) seeing dramatic reductions in their intangible asset scores. These declines suggest a lack of investment in key sectors such as education, intellectual property protection, and technological innovation, alongside structural difficulties related to poverty, political instability, and inadequate infrastructure.

In many cases, the lack of progress in these sectors is directly linked to a low priority given to managing and developing intangible assets, making it difficult for these countries to compete globally. Another element worth noting is the decline of Eastern European countries, such as the Czech Republic (-44.9%) and Lithuania (-46.3%), which saw significant drops in their scores. This could reflect the impact of the economic recession following the global financial crisis and the slow recovery compared to more advanced economies. Countries like Estonia, traditionally a leader in digital innovation, lost 30.4%, perhaps highlighting a stagnation in their ability to expand the intangible economy in an increasingly competitive global context. Finally, looking at Latin American countries, nations such as Argentina (-28.1%), Chile (-27.6%), and Mexico (-21.2%) experienced significant declines in their management of intangible assets, likely due to internal economic crises and political instability, which have hindered progress in strategic innovation sectors. Similarly, countries like Brazil (-11.3%) have struggled to keep pace with global demand for innovation. In summary, the data shows that while some emerging economies have made great strides in valuing their intangible assets, many countries, especially those less developed or in transition, struggle to keep up. Growth in intangible assets is closely tied to economic, political, and institutional factors, and the data suggests that countries that strategically invest in human capital, research and development, and intellectual property protection tend to register the greatest improvements. On the other hand, political instability, weak infrastructure, and a lack of investment in technology and education severely limit countries' ability to exploit the potential of intangible assets.

Economic Policies for Intangible Assets. The development of intangible assets on a global scale requires the adoption of targeted and strategic economic policies that encourage innovation, human capital, and the protection of intellectual property. Intangible assets, such as intellectual property, patents, trademarks, industrial design, and technological know-how, represent a crucial resource for economic growth in the modern economy, especially in an era where knowledge and innovation are the main competitive levers. Economic policies should therefore focus on various aspects that promote the creation, use, and protection of these immaterial goods. A fundamental approach is to invest in human capital, which is at the core of intangible asset development. Governments must promote robust education systems, with a particular emphasis on scientific and technological training, innovation, and the development of specific skills required in high-tech sectors. Creating a modern education system that supports research and innovation is essential for developing the skills that drive the growth of knowledge-based industries. Additionally, continuous updating and retraining of workers must become a priority to enable them to adapt to rapid technological changes. Another key pillar for the development of intangible assets is increasing investment in research and development (R&D). Economic policies must incentivize both the private and public sectors to invest in R&D, offering tax incentives, targeted funding, and public-private partnerships. Companies that invest in R&D tend to develop new technologies, patents, and innovations that become the foundation of intangible assets. A favorable environment for research investments stimulates the creation of new ideas, technological solutions, and innovative products that can be marketed globally. Moreover, the creation of scientific and technological excellence centers, funded by governments, fosters collaboration between universities, companies, and research institutions. At the same time, policies protecting intellectual property play a crucial role in developing intangible assets. Patent, trademark, and copyright regulations must be modern, clear, and efficiently enforced to protect innovations and products of intellectual creativity. A strong protection system increases investor confidence, encouraging companies to innovate knowing that their discoveries will be safeguarded. Furthermore, international cooperation in this area is critical since intangible assets are often global in nature. A

harmonized international regulatory framework could reduce costs for companies operating in multiple markets, improving access to intellectual property protection and reducing bureaucratic barriers. To further support the development of intangible assets, it is important to create dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystems that promote innovation and the growth of startups. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and startups, particularly those in the technology sector, are often at the forefront of developing intangible assets such as software, algorithms, patents, and creative solutions. Governments should promote access to funding for these businesses through venture capital funds, tax incentives for innovative startups, and accelerator programs. Additionally, creating technology clusters and science parks that connect universities, businesses, and investors can create a fertile environment for innovation. These technology hubs provide the necessary infrastructure and facilitate collaboration, accelerating the development of new intangible assets and their commercialization. Another important area of intervention is digitalization and the development of technological infrastructure. Intangible assets are often linked to advanced technologies, and a solid network of digital infrastructure is essential for their development. Governments must invest in infrastructure such as high-speed broadband, cloud systems, and artificial intelligence platforms to allow companies to develop and market digital innovations. The digitization of production processes and services not only improves business efficiency but also paves the way for creating new intangible assets, such as advanced software and data-based technologies. Fiscal and regulatory policies also play an important role. Governments can introduce specific tax incentives for companies that invest in R&D or produce intangible goods. These incentives can reduce development costs and encourage companies to invest more in innovative activities. Moreover, flexible and pro-innovation regulatory policies that facilitate market access for new technologies and reduce bureaucratic barriers can accelerate the development of intangible assets. Smart regulation can also help businesses balance innovation with legal compliance, reducing the risk of sanctions and regulatory hurdles. International cooperation is essential to maximize the development of intangible assets. International trade agreements that include intellectual property protection and innovation incentives can facilitate the exchange of knowledge and technology between nations, stimulating economic growth globally. Cooperation on topics such as scientific research, vocational training, and the development of international standards for intellectual property can create a more favorable context for innovation worldwide, allowing companies to access larger markets and leverage global synergies. Finally, it is essential that governments promote a culture of innovation within their economies. This culture must permeate the education system, economic policies, and society in general, encouraging individuals and businesses to experiment, create, and share new ideas. Policies that incentivize social innovation, creativity, and collaboration across sectors and industries can foster an environment where intangible assets develop more rapidly. Support for events such as hackathons, innovation contests, and discussion forums can create a vibrant community of innovators ready to turn their ideas into tangible economic value. In conclusion, developing intangible assets globally requires a coherent set of economic policies encompassing education, research, intellectual property protection, digitalization, and international cooperation. Only through a strategic commitment in these areas can governments and businesses fully harness the potential of intangible assets, stimulating economic growth and improving long-term competitiveness.

Conclusions. The global level of intangible assets for the countries considered decreased from 44.09 units in 2013 to 29.75 units in 2022, with a reduction of 32.53%. Some countries have significantly increased their intangible asset value during this period, such as Iran (+144.7%), South Korea (+96.60%), China (+93.7%), Turkey (+82.80%), and France (+74.80%). However, there are countries where the value of intangible assets decreased more than the average between 2013 and 2022,

including Ethiopia (-96.40%), Burkina Faso (-96.50%), Cameroon (-96.70%), Mali (-98.40%), and Benin (-99.20%).

Countries	2022	Countries	2022	Countries	2022
Korea, Rep.	85,7	Kuwait	37	Ghana	16,4
China	82,9	Argentina	36,9	Ecuador	16,3
France	76,9	Belgium	36	Guatemala	14,7
Turkiye	72,2	Thailand	35,6	Slovak Republic	14,6
Malta	69,6	Mexico	35,4	Botswana	14,4
United Kingdom	68,3	Paraguay	35,3	Uruguay	13,9
Germany	67,8	Qatar	34,8	Bahrain	13,5
Switzerland	63,5	Pakistan	34,3	Uzbekistan	12,4
Italy	62,2	South Africa	34,3	Mozambique	12
Iran, Islamic Rep.	60,2	Singapore	34	Cote d'Ivoire	11,3
Jamaica	60,2	United Arab Emirates	33,5	Zambia	11,2
Bulgaria	59	Norway	32,9	Algeria	10,5
Sweden	57,4	Saudi Arabia	32,2	Dominican Republic	10,3
Hong Kong SAR, China	54,7	Peru	31,4	Azerbaijan	10
Japan	53,8	Greece	31	Nepal	10
United States	52,8	Indonesia	30,4	Cambodia	9,9
Luxembourg	51,7	Croatia	30,2	Nicaragua	9,8
Mauritius	51,6	Philippines	30	Albania	9,2
Portugal	51,2	Ukraine	29,7	Myanmar	9,2
Denmark	50,9	Romania	28,5	Belarus	7,6
Netherlands	50,8	Israel	27,3	Honduras	7,6
Spain	50,6	Hungary	26,8	North Macedonia	7,2
Morocco	49,5	Colombia	26,4	Angola	7
Mongolia	48,5	Oman	25,2	Montenegro	7
Cyprus	46,7	Bangladesh	24,5	Guinea	6,8
Finland	46	Lithuania	24,5	Trinidad and Tobago	6,7
New Zealand	44,9	Czechia	24,1	Tanzania	6,5
Vietnam	44,9	Armenia	23,3	Namibia	5,8
Moldova	44,8	Egypt, Arab Rep.	23,3	Kazakhstan	5,4
Austria	43,8	Jordan	22,4	Senegal	4,5
Australia	43,3	Serbia	21,6	Kyrgyz Republic	4
Iceland	41,9	El Salvador	21,3	Uganda	3,9
Brazil	41,8	Yemen, Rep.	20,7	Rwanda	3,2
Ireland	41,2	Sri Lanka	20,6	Togo	2,8
Russian Federation	40	Bosnia and Herzegovina	20,5	Tajikistan	2,8

Canada	39,9	Costa Rica	20,4	Brunei Darussalam	2,1
Estonia	39,6	Slovenia	20,2	Lao PDR	1,9
Chile	39,3	Nigeria	19,4	Burkina Faso	1,5
Poland	38,6	Latvia	18,5	Cameroon	1,5
India	38	Georgia	17,8	Ethiopia	1,5
Malaysia	38	Kenya	17,7	Burundi	0,9
Madagascar	37,6	Zimbabwe	17,7	Mali	0,9
Tunisia	37,5	Panama	17,1	Iraq	0,7

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